

A Study on Factors Associated with Cesarean Delivery in Post Term Pregnancy Following Labor Induction in ACSR Government Medical College, Nellore

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Abstract:

Background: Post term pregnancy is delivery at or beyond 42 weeks of gestation. The prevalence varies worldwide is 5–10%. The best time for labor induction remains a controversy. Earlier induction may result in a higher proportion of induction failure followed by cesarean section, whereas the risk of poor maternal and fetal outcome increases with gestational age.

Aim of the Study is to investigate factors associated with Cesarean Delivery in post-term pregnancy following labor induction.

Materials and Methods: It was a Population-based cohort study. A total of 780 pregnant cases who reached 41 weeks gestation and admitted for delivery in the Department of OBG, ACSR Government Medical College, and Nellore between 2018 to 2023 were studied. Patients were studied for assessing the factors for Cesarean delivery in those who underwent induction of Labour. Women with any medical or obstetric risk factors were excluded.

Results: Among 780 cases that had Labour induction 420 cases (53.8%) had Vaginal Delivery and 360 cases ended in Cesarean Delivery for following indications. Failed Induction in 26.7%, Meconium stained liquor in 33.3%, at request in 10%, Non-Reactive CTG in 10%, genital warts in 3.3%, card round the neck in 3.3%, Oligohydramnios in 13.4%.

Conclusion: Factors like failed induction and fetal distress, were the cause of excess cesarean deliveries in women with prolonged pregnancies in our study.

Keywords: Post Term pregnancy, Induction, Cesarean Section, Factors.

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Introduction

Post term pregnancy is defined as delivery beyond 42 weeks of gestation. [1] The Prevalence varies from 5–10% worldwide. [2] Routine ultrasound examination for dating has reduced the incidence of post term pregnancy significantly. [3] There is always an increased risk for fetal and maternal side making its management an important issue. [4,5] The best time for labor induction remains a controversy. Earlier induction may result in a higher proportion of induction failure followed by cesarean section, whereas the risk of poor maternal and fetal outcome increases with gestational age. [6] The rate of labor induction is increasing worldwide [7] and this increases the rate of Cesarean Sections due to induction Failure. [8] Maternal characteristics (i.e. Parity and age), play a role independently beside cervical changes for failed labor induction. [9]

Aim of the Study is to investigate factors associated with Cesarean Delivery in post-term pregnancy following labor induction.

Material and Methods

It was a Population-based cohort study. A total of 780 women who reached 41 weeks gestation were studied between 2018 to 2023. Patients were studied for assessing the factors for Cesarean delivery in those who underwent induction of Labour. Women with any medical or obstetric risk factors were excluded. Demographic data was collected. Patients were induced by various methods and those who underwent section, the factors leading to section were analyzed.

Results

Table 1: Relation between Age and Parity in the study

Age Group	15 -25 Years	25-35 Years	Total
Primi Gravida	260 (33.3%)	52 (6.7%)	312 (40%)
Multi Gravida	28 (3.6%)	440 (56.4%)	468 (60%)
Total	288 (36.9%)	492 (63.1%)	780 (100%)

Table 2: Distribution of Fetal Weight in the study

Fetal Weight	Number
< 2kg	12 (1.5%)
< 3 kg	312 (40%)
>3 kg	456 (58.5%)
Total	780 (100%)

Table 3: Distribution of Mode of Delivery in the study

Mode of deliver	Cesarean Section	Vaginal Delivery	Total
Primi Gravida	276 (35.4%)	36 (4.6%)	312 (40%)
Multi Gravida	84 (10.8%)	384 (49.2%)	468 (60%)
Total	360 (46.2%)	420 (53.8%)	780 (100%)

Table 4: Indications for Cesarean Delivery in the study

Indications for LSCS	Number
Failed Induction	96 (26.7%)
Meconium Stained	120 (33.3%)
At Request	36 (10%)
Non-Reactive CTG	36 (10%)
Genital Wart	12 (3.3%)
Cord Round Neck	12 (3.3%)
Oligohydramnios	48 (13.4%)
Total	360 (100%)

Table 5: Induction Methods in Vaginal Delivery in the study

Normal delivery Induction Type	Number
Foleys Misoprostol	96 (22.8%)
Misoprostol	60 (14.5%)
Stripping	48 (11.4%)
Misoprostol Oxytocin	72 (17.1%)
Spontaneous	120 (28.6%)
Oxytocin	12 (2.8%)
Head on Perineum	12 (2.8%)
Total	420 (100%)

Discussion

In our study the rate of post term pregnancy increased with increasing maternal age in a dose dependent manner which is supported by most previous studies. [10,11] 492 cases (63.1%) were between 25-35 years. But maternal age did not influence risk of post term pregnancy in a study by Olesen et al. [12] Advanced maternal age >35 years more than doubled the risk of Cesarean Section following labor induction in post-term pregnancy.

Similar findings have been reported in studies of failure of induction not restricted to post term pregnancies [13], whereas this was not observed in a study by Cnattingius et al. [14] Advanced maternal age is an independent risk factor for

Cesarean Section independently of labor starting spontaneously or by induction. 15 Older parturients have a higher incidence of non-progressive labor and more often require oxytocin in higher doses and for longer periods of time to achieve vaginal delivery compared to younger women. [16]

Primiparity was an independent risk factor for prolonged pregnancy consistent with previous findings. [12,17] In 312 (40%) Primigravida cases, 276 (35.4%) cases had Cesarean Section and 36 (4.6%) cases had vaginal delivery. In 468 (60%) Multigravida cases 84 (10.8%) had Cesarean section and 384 (49.2%) cases had vaginal delivery.

Primipara was associated with a fivefold increased risk for Cesarean Section following labor induction among post term pregnancies constituting almost one-third of all failures. This is in line with prior studies on term pregnancies. [18,19,20,21] Primiparous women often require oxytocin augmentation to achieve a vaginal delivery. A previous pregnancy may have induced a higher number of gap junctions in the myometrium, giving rise to a shorter second stage of labor in parous women. [18]

Cesarean Section following labor induction is associated with an increased risk of complications for both neonate and mother. [22,23] Among the 780 babies 12 babies were < 2kg (1.5%), 312 (40%) had < 3kg birth weight, 456 (58.5%) had >3kg birth weight. Cervical assessment prior to labor induction is used to predict the likelihood of vaginal delivery.

Among 780 cases that had Labour induction 420 cases (53.8%) had Vaginal Delivery and 360 cases ended in Cesarean Delivery for following indications. Failed Induction in 26.7%, Meconium stained liquor in 33.3%, at request in 10%, Breech position in 10%, genital warts in 3.3%, card round the neck in 3.3%, Oligohydramnios in 13.4%.

Among the 420 cases who had vaginal delivery following induction, Foleys with Misoprostol was used in 96 cases (22.8%), Misoprostol alone in 60 cases (14.5%), Stripping of membranes in 48 cases (11.4%), Misoprostol and Oxytocin in 72 cases (17.1%), Spontaneous in 120 cases (28.6%), Oxytocin alone in 12 cases(2.8%).

Few studies have investigated the failure of labor induction in post-term pregnancies by taking maternal characteristics as well as cervical assessment into account. [13,21] From our study the maternal factors like parity and advanced maternal age were associated with increased risk of post term pregnancy and Cesarean Section following labor induction. Factors like failed induction and fetal distress, were the cause of excess cesarean deliveries in women with prolonged pregnancies in our study.

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